

Why Invest in Real Estate?

Have you ever wondered why when we talk about investing in real estate we always use the phrase secure your future?

Of course at a glance we can understand that real estate investment is a safer way to grow our money and one of the easiest if we take into account that not all of us know how the stock market works.

[Seasoned entrepreneur](#), Moshe Junger, who is experienced in real estate investing, indicates that realacquiring a property, even when you do not plan to live in it, can be more beneficial than leaving your money saved in the bank, especially if you acquire one that is located in an area whose capital gains foresees a considerable increase.

However, investing in real estate can sound a bit scary and more when we do not have experience in the field: legal procedures, long payment terms, even the fear of not wanting to be tied to a place where we do not know if we are eventually going to stay.

This happens a lot to millennials. What is the best age to invest in real estate? Here Moshe Junger talks a little about the subject. The orange economy, that is, the creative one, makes jobs more and more informal and varied, and while millennials value experiences more than acquiring objects, the reality is that they are one of the generations that should be most concerned about creating an investment portfolio and start thinking about your future.

[Moshe Junger](#) indicates that there are many factors that do not favor millennials and their future at all. For example, economic and environmental conditions; It is believed that unlike generations like baby boomers - and even Gen X - millennials could only retire until they were 75 years old.

In the same way, the conditions of retirement and education do not favor them. Although it could be considered one of the generations with the most technological developments and with the greatest access to education, many millennials struggle to pay their school debts and their income.

And not just millennials, more and more people are beginning to worry about increasing their money before retirement thanks to changes and restructuring of pension plans or the lack of them.

Faced with such a bleak vision, it is normal to think that investing in real estate is impossible, even though this could be one of the best ways to guarantee our future.

Although uncertainty surrounds us all, it is millennials - who are between 35 and 23 years old - and centennials who are becoming more and more concerned about how to start investing, from now on.

Moshe Junger, basing on [his wide experience in the real estate sector](#), indicates that, unlike previous generations who began saving and investing for retirement between their 30s and 35s, it is believed that millennials start saving in their 20s and are the ones who are more interested in finding more beneficial solutions for their future than simply saving more than your ancestors did for their pay.